

A Programmable Filtering and Frequency Translation by Aliasing IF Receiver with Alias- and Harmonic-Rejection

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Abstract—A programmable intermediate frequency receiver is proposed employing a sampler, time-varying capacitor and switched-capacitor integrator. It realizes high-order finite impulse response low-pass or band-pass filtering and frequency translation with harmonic rejection. The receiver’s center frequency and bandwidth can be independently programmed across the Nyquist zone. The primary focus is on balancing filter stop-band rejection with harmonic, image, and alias rejection in a prototype 28nm CMOS chip design. This work is also the first to address and quantify the adjacent and alternate adjacent channel aliasing in filtering by aliasing filters. The center frequency and bandwidth of the receiver can be programmed to 0 - 1 GHz and 8 - 25 MHz, respectively. The receiver achieves a wideband impedance matching $S_{11} < -9$ dB across the first Nyquist zone. It employs 8-bit filter coefficients to achieve consistent > 50 dB stop-band attenuation at $1\times$ bandwidth offset, harmonic rejection, image rejection and 50 dB in-band alias suppression. The I and Q receiver uses only a single fixed 1 GHz clock frequency to achieve all the functionality and consumes 73.6 mW.

Index Terms—Active filters, bandpass filters, CMOS integrated circuits, filtering by aliasing, FIR filters, harmonic rejection, intermediate frequency, radio transceivers, sampled data circuits, sub-sampling, switched capacitor circuits, time-varying circuits, time-varying capacitors and tunable circuits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile communication networks are continuously pushed to support more users at higher data rates. However, the sub - 6 GHz spectrum is crowded, while 28 GHz and 38 GHz systems for 5G are still costly and power-hungry. Hence, frequency bands from 7 - 24 GHz are explored, even if limited contiguous bandwidth is available there [1]. Zero Intermediate Frequency (IF) architectures are widely used in the sub - 6 GHz regime, but designing quadrature clocks at higher frequencies is challenging and imposes stringent constraints on Local Oscillator phase noise and power [1]. Furthermore,

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Fig. 1. Proposed programmable FTA IF receiver as a BPF + FT or LPF configuration. The blocks within the grey box represent actual chip implementation.

as the available spectrum in the 7-24 GHz bands is limited, spectral efficiency and avoiding filter guard bands will be critical, resulting in stringent adjacent and alternate adjacent channel selectivity [2]. Moreover, carrier aggregation and a recently proposed time-modulated array technique produce a set of concurrent IF-frequency channels which challenge Analog to Digital Converters (ADC) and digital processing requirements [3]. Driven by these trends and the desire to support various IF scenarios, this work explores a flexible IF receiver exploiting Filtering and Frequency Translation by Aliasing (FTA). It realizes a programmable center frequency and channel bandwidth while achieving exceptional adjacent and alternate adjacent channel selectivity. We aim to support a zero IF by highly programmable Low Pass Filtering (LPF by “Filtering-by-Aliasing” - FA) as well as a high IF by Band Pass Filtering (BPF), followed by frequency translation (FTA). This work does not target a specific standard but aims to evaluate the feasibility of the concept and its performance limits in the arbitrarily chosen 0 - 1 GHz band (shown in a grey box in Fig. 1). The requirements on the 1st stage RF filter (see Fig. 1) are also important for overall feasibility, but they are not within the scope of this work, as they heavily depend on the chosen

RF band and the associated interference level, particularly in the image channel. Note, however, that a programmable IF receiver will allow for adaptation in frequency planning to avoid or reduce interference from image bands.

Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) or passive LC filters are traditionally used at the IF since they offer superior linearity and adjacent channel selectivity. However, they are not programmable, have a relatively large silicon footprint, and are more expensive than CMOS chips. Hence, CMOS-compatible programmable low/band-pass filters and frequency translation are desired.

When compared to Radio Frequency (RF) receiver specifications, at IF, the noise specification is relaxed due to gain in preceding RF blocks [4], but the Harmonic Rejection (HR) becomes a stringent requirement [5]. Our design goal is an IF receiver architecture with widely programmable center frequency, bandwidth (BW), harmonic rejection low/band-pass filtering with high adjacent and alternate adjacent channel selectivity and frequency translation.

Transconductance- C ($g_m C$) and active RC filters have been well researched but are PVT sensitive and especially band-pass filters are not widely programmable [4]. Band-pass N -path filters [9], [10], [11], [12] do have wide-range center frequency programmability, but have limitations in filter roll-off and harmonic folding. To alleviate the problem of harmonic folding, a Discrete Time (DT) charge-sharing-based Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) BPF was proposed in [5], [13]. However, its center frequency has limited programmability. Moreover, sharp adjacent channel filtering remains challenging.

Recently, DT Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filters (FA filters) have achieved sharp higher-order filtering with independent control over the center frequency, bandwidth and stop-band attenuation, as shown in Fig. 2(a) and 2(b). These FA filters use a fixed capacitor and a time-varying R or g_m to realize FIR filter weights [6], [14], [15], [16], [7]. Integration over long time blocks followed by sub-sampling allows for sharp higher-order filtering. However, sub-sampling leads to aliasing within the BW (in-band). Also, prior FA filters use a passive mixer to upconvert the LPF Transfer Function (TF) to BPF TF, introducing harmonic folding. The work in [14] combines a passive mixer with a sinusoidal coefficient to achieve HR. However, due to the parasitic capacitance of the time-varying R , the achieved HR is < 25 dB.

This work is the first to quantify and design for adjacent and alternate adjacent channel aliasing (in-band aliasing) and harmonic rejection in FA-based IF receivers. In addition, we demonstrate sharp FIR Filtering and frequency Translation by exploiting Aliasing (FTA) with programmable center frequency, bandwidth and channel selection. We also explore Switched Capacitor (SC) sampling and SC charge domain weighing for FIR filter coefficients, hoping to leverage known good CMOS capacitor properties like linearity, high density and good matching. The proposed programmable FTA circuit is shown in Fig. 2(c) and targets:

- 1) IF sampling at $f_s = 1$ GHz from a 50Ω source
- 2) 50Ω input impedance across the Nyquist zone
- 3) Programmable center frequency (f_c) from 0 - 1 GHz
- 4) Programmable channel bandwidth 10 - 100 MHz

- 5) > 50 dB stop-band attenuation at $1 \times$ BW offset
- 6) > 50 dB In-Band Alias Suppression (IBAS)
- 7) > 50 dB Image Rejection (IR) with single trim calibration
- 8) > 50 dB wideband HR across the Nyquist zone
- 9) Frequency translation of the IF input to zero/low IF with quadrature outputs.

Moreover, only a single fixed clock is required, avoiding issues with multiple clock domains [17]. This is particularly relevant when several concurrent receiver chains are implemented in the SoC (in the case of carrier aggregation). Prior work [6], [7], [14], [15] did demonstrate high stop-band rejection but shows poor adjacent and alternate adjacent channel alias suppression (worst case only 3 dB, as will be discussed in Section II-B). This work aims for well-balanced performance, with > 50 dB stop-band attenuation, > 50 dB IR and > 50 dB HR across the Nyquist zone while keeping aliasing in check (> 50 dB in-band alias suppression).

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system-level design choices and trade-offs. Section III discusses the architecture of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver. Section IV discusses the circuit details and non-idealities of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver. Section V presents the measurement results. Section VI summarizes the work with concluding remarks.

II. SYSTEM LEVEL DESIGN AND TRADE-OFF

The following subsection will briefly compare the proposed FTA and prior FA to clarify the differences at the circuit level and the trade-offs. In addition, a detailed discussion on in-band alias suppression in FA filters, harmonic rejection, filter reconfigurability and frequency translation by aliasing is presented.

A. Comparison of the FTA and FA Architecture

Fig. 2(a), 2(b) show circuit-level implementations of FA and 2(c) for FTA. In Fig. 2(a) and 2(b), the input is first downconverted to the baseband by a Continuous Time (CT) mixer. The baseband input is then low-pass filtered using the FA filter. The low-pass filter coefficients $\alpha(t)$ (it is in CT since the input V_{in} is also in CT) and corresponding transfer function are shown in Fig. 2(d) [6], [7], [8]. The FA filter output is sub-sampled at f_{sub} , leading to aliasing. Both FA circuit architectures use time-varying RC or $g_m C$ for filtering. In this proposed FTA implementation, a time-varying C ratio is used for better matching properties. In the FTA system, as shown in Fig. 2(c), first, the input is sampled at a rate f_s . The FTA system can be configured as both a band-pass or low-pass filter configuration. In the case of band-pass filter configuration, the sampled input is weighted according to band-pass filter coefficients $\beta[n]$ (it is in discrete sequence since the input V_{in} is sampled and is in DT), as shown in Fig. 2(e) and integrated by an SC integrator. The output of the SC integrator is sub-sampled at f_{sub} , similar to the FA filter. In the FTA system, the sub-sampling frequency translates the input to a zero/low IF. In the case of low-pass filter configuration, the sampled input is weighted according to the low-pass filter coefficients (discrete sequence).

Fig. 2. (a) Time-varying R and integrator to implement FIR filtering [6]. (b) Time-varying g_m with $g_m C$ integrator to implement FIR filtering [7], [8]. (c) Proposed time-varying capacitor and SC integrator to implement FIR filtering. (d) Low-pass FIR filter coefficients and its corresponding transfer function [6], [7], [8]. (e) Proposed band-pass FIR filter coefficients and its corresponding transfer function.

Fig. 3. A N -tap FA architecture with multiplication, summation and sub-sampling.

Fig. 4. Second Nyquist zone alias strengths (markers) for varying number of TI path ($M=1, 2, 3, 4$) and folding frequency (2.5 - 10 MHz).

B. In-band Alias Suppression

Sub-sampling is inherent to FA and FTA based receivers to allow for high-order analog FIR filtering over a long time block with limited hardware complexity [6], [7]. Fig. 3 illustrates this FIR concept: the input $x[n]$ is first multiplied by filter coefficients $\alpha[n]$, then summed over filter length N and sub-sampled at rate $f_{sub} = f_s/N$. However, sub-sampling leads to aliasing¹, which may corrupt the wanted signal and increase the noise floor. The work in [6], [7] used M hardware slices in a Time-Interleaved (TI) architecture to increase the output sub-sampling rate by M times to satisfy the Nyquist criterion ($2 \times$ Baseband Bandwidth (BW_{BB})). However, $M = 2$ is not sufficient to suppress adjacent and alternate adjacent channel aliases significantly. Fig. 4 illustrates an example of an FA filter ($f_s = 1$ GHz, $N = 200$ and $f_{sub} = 5$ MHz) in which the second Nyquist zone aliases to the signal BW_{BB} for a different number of TI paths M . As M varies from 1 - 4, f_{sub} ranges from 5 - 20 MHz. Consequently, the folding frequency changes (2.5 - 10 MHz), improving alias suppression within the BW_{BB} from 0 to > 50 dB, as shown in Fig. 4. For $M > 4$, the alias suppression remains constant and equal to the stop-band attenuation of the filter. In this example, four TI paths are chosen to achieve targeted and maximum achievable alias suppression for a given stop-band attenuation. The Signal-to-Interference ratio (SIR) then becomes:

¹As the name FA suggests; However, aliasing is obviously not the goal. A better description is "Filtering Allowing for some Aliasing," where the aliases are kept in check by prefiltering and interleaving.

$$\text{SIR [dB]} = P_{\text{signal}} [\text{dBm}] - P_{\text{blocker}} [\text{dBm}] + H(f_{\text{blocker}}) [\text{dB}] \quad (1)$$

where P_{signal} is signal power, P_{blocker} is blocker power and $H(f_{\text{blocker}})$ is the magnitude of filter TF at the blocker frequency. For example, if desired $\text{SIR} = 20$ dB and $P_{\text{blocker}} = P_{\text{signal}} + 30$ dB, the required filter attenuation can be as high as 50 dB. To keep aliasing attenuated to the stop-band attenuation of the filter, $f_{\text{sub},\text{min}}$ should be:

$$f_{\text{sub},\text{min}} \geq f_{\text{stopband}} + BW_{\text{BB}} \quad (2)$$

where f_{stopband} is the stop-band frequency and BW_{BB} is the baseband bandwidth. Prior FA architectures only chose the f_{sub} twice the BW_{BB} , which resulted in worst-case alias suppression of 3 dB (similar to alias strength of two TI paths in Fig. 4) [6], [7], [14], [15].

Improving IBAS could involve incorporating a conventional anti-aliasing filter in front of the FA receiver. However, achieving $\text{IBAS} > 50$ dB for the adjacent channel is impractical due to the lack of guard bands for filter transition. For the work in [6], the filter achieves ≈ 20 dB attenuation at alternate adjacent channels, necessitating an additional 30 dB filtering at only $1 \times \text{RF Bandwidth}$ ($BW_{\text{RF}} = 2 \times BW_{\text{BB}}$). The work in [12], [10], [4] can be utilized as an anti-alias filter in front of a conventional FA filter. However, as discussed in Section I, they either suffer from harmonic folding [12], [10] or limited tuning range [4].

One might wonder whether increasing the first sampler frequency f_s helps to increase f_{sub} (refer to Fig. 3). This is not the case, as the number of filter coefficients N will also need to increase to keep the same BW_{BB} and transition band, thereby leaving f_{sub} unaffected. Decreasing N would result in a trade-off in the filter's transition band or stop-band attenuation, making it an unsuitable solution. Hence we propose to increase the number of TI paths (M).

This work aim for $\text{IBAS} > 50$ dB. We also estimated what earlier work would need to achieve $\text{IBAS} > 50$ dB. A rough calculation shows that the work in [6] would require $f_{\text{sub},\text{min}} = 35$ MHz, calculated using Eq. 2 and their filter TF (refer to Fig. 17 in [6]). This would require seven TI paths ($f_{\text{sub}} = 5$ MHz for one TI path in [6]), resulting in a total power consumption of 346.5 mW and an area > 8 mm². This work aims to do better in power and area for targetted $\text{IBAS} > 50$ dB.

C. Harmonic Rejection

In FA architecture, a passive mixer is used to downconvert the input (f_{if}) to the baseband. Passive mixers use square wave clocks, resulting in harmonic folding. To tackle the above problem, in FTA systems, first, a harmonic-suppressed band-pass filter is realized by upconverting the LPF TF using a single-tone sinusoid, as shown in Fig. 2(e). Second, the band-pass filtered output is frequency translated to zero/low IF by sub-sampling. Hence, sub-sampling aliases are attenuated before they fold back to the output signal BW.

Fig. 5. Simulated BPF TF tuned for different center frequencies across the Nyquist zone ($f_s = 1$ GHz) in steps for 100 MHz.

Fig. 6. Simulated BPF TF ($f_c = 250$ MHz) for varying the number of filter coefficients ($N = 20$ to 200). The BW_{RF} of the BPF varies from 100 MHz to 10 MHz when N varies from 20 to 200, respectively.

In the case of FTA, there is a fundamental trade-off between HR and Noise Figure (NF) if a sinusoidal multiplication is used instead of a square multiplication to suppress all the harmonics of f_{lo} . Fundamentally, a sinusoidal multiplication leads to a sum ($f_{if} + f_{lo}$) and difference ($f_{if} - f_{lo}$) frequency component each with $0.5 \times$ amplitude, i.e., 6 dB loss in Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), which translates to a 6 dB increment in NF .

D. Filter Configuration and Programmability

Fig. 1 shows different scenarios in which the proposed FTA-based IF receiver architecture is configured as a band-pass or low-pass filter. These different configurations are achieved by modifying the FIR coefficients. In case 1, the first downconversion stage is high IF; the proposed FTA is configured as a band-pass filter and Frequency Translation (FT) (as will be discussed in Section II-E). The FTA-based IF receiver, in this case, filters (band-pass) the input, and frequency translates the IF input to zero/low IF. In case 2, the first downconversion stage is zero IF; the proposed FTA is configured as a low-pass filter. In this case, the FTA-based IF receiver only filters (low-pass) the IF input.

In addition to filter reconfigurability, the centre frequency (f_c) and the BW of the BPF or LPF can also be varied by varying the filter coefficients. Fig. 5 shows the simulated BPF TF for different centre frequencies f_c across the Nyquist zone

Fig. 7. Different cases of frequency translation of the input to zero/low IF due to sub-sampling.

for $f_s = 1$ GHz. In the case of $f_c = 200$ MHz, the stop-band attenuation profile is shown across the entire Nyquist zone. A stop-band attenuation > 50 dB at a frequency offset of only $1 \times BW_{RF}$ is achieved, and HR > 50 dB at all the harmonics of the f_c in the entire Nyquist zone. The filter coefficient's quantization and accuracies set the stop-band attenuation limit. This work chooses an 8-bit filter coefficient; hence, the stop-band attenuation is limited to 50 dB. Fig. 6 shows the programmability in BW_{RF} from 10 - 100 MHz when N goes down from 200 - 20. Although the number of filter coefficients is reduced, the normalized transition bandwidth ($1 \times BW_{RF}$) and IBAS (> 50 dB) remain constant because f_{sub} is also varied accordingly.

E. Frequency Translation

The inherent sub-sampling in FTA systems frequency translates the signal to zero or low IF, depending on the IF input. Fig. 7(a), 7(b), 7(c) shows the different scenarios of frequency translation depending on the IF input.

Zero IF: IF input frequencies around f_{sub} , $2f_{sub}$, $n \cdot f_{sub}$ (where 'n' is an integer) gets frequency translated to DC, i.e., zero-IF. Fig. 7(a) shows an example for an IF input (S) around $2f_{sub}$. Blocker A is also frequency translated to DC but attenuated by BPF TF.

Low IF: IF input frequencies around $0.25f_{sub}$, $0.75f_{sub}$, $n \cdot f_{sub} \pm 0.25f_{sub}$ gets translated to $0.25f_{sub}$. Similarly, input frequencies around $n \cdot f_{sub}/2$ gets translated to $f_{sub}/2$, i.e., low-IF. Fig. 7(b) shows an example for IF input (S) around $1.75f_{sub}$ and Fig. 7(c) for $1.5f_{sub}$. To resolve signal components translated to multiple Nyquist zones, we need I and Q paths (as will be discussed in Section III) to achieve image rejection at the output, which is needed for zero-IF anyway.

F. Code-independent Input Matching

Prior FA architectures with time-varying RC [6], [14] have a code-dependent (filter coefficients dependent) impedance matching, which adds complexity to filter design and also limiting in case of carrier aggregation scenario [15]. The work in [15] uses a fixed R and time-varying g_m at the input to achieve code-independent matching. However, the architecture is limited to implementing only positive coefficients and hence cannot be adopted for sinusoidal coefficients, which would need both positive and negative coefficients. To overcome the above problem, in the proposed FTA architecture, the input is sampled on a constant capacitor C_s . Charge domain weighing implements both positive and negative coefficients after the sampling, hence achieving code-independent input matching, as in [18].

III. PROPOSED FILTERING AND FREQUENCY TRANSLATION BY ALIASING-BASED IF RECEIVER

This section explains the proposed FTA architecture in detail. Subsection III-A discusses the proposed FTA-based IF receiver's architecture and timing diagram. Subsection III-B discusses the programmable digital architecture to store and read the FIR coefficients and control signal.

A. FTA-based IF Receiver

Fig. 8 shows the circuit-level implementation of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver, timing diagram and FIR coefficients (I and Q). It consists of a sampler, a time-varying capacitor (C_1 & C_2), an SC integrator and a sub-sampler. The SC integrator is implemented with auto-zeroing and uses an inverter-based g_m -block with cross-coupled g_m 's to increase the DC gain. Auto-zeroing reduces offset and $1/f$ noise of the inverters. As discussed in Section II, multiplication of the input with filter coefficients, summation over filter length and sub-sampling realize filtering and frequency translation. The above operations are sequentially executed in the proposed FTA receiver in four phases: sampling, summation, sub-sampling, and reset, which are defined and described below.

Sampling: Sampling clock $\Phi_s = 1$, bias clock $\Phi_b = 1$, summation clock $\Phi_{sum} = 1$, sub-sampling clock $\Phi_{sub} = 0$, reset clock $\Phi_{res} = 0$ and charge transfer clock $\Phi_t = 0$. The IF input V_{IF} is sampled on all parallel connected capacitors C_1 and C_2 ($C_1 = C_2 = C_s$), with sampling frequency f_s . The clock jitter requirement of the sampling clock Φ_s is similar to mixer's phase noise requirements in more conventional RF systems [19]. The g_m -block is self-biased now, producing a common-mode voltage V_{cm} which is sampled on the auto-zero bias capacitor C_b , along with offset and $1/f$ noise.

Summation: $\Phi_s = 0$, $\Phi_b = 0$, $\Phi_{sum} = 1$, $\Phi_{sub} = 0$, $\Phi_{res} = 0$ and $\Phi_t = 1$. Now, weighing code $\beta[n]$ defines how sampling capacitor C_1 is split into mC_1 and $(1-m)C_1$, while the sampling capacitor C_2 is split into mC_2 and $(1-m)C_2$. The capacitors mC_1 and $(1-m)C_2$ are now connected to node V_x , and mC_2 and $(1-m)C_1$ to V_y . As a result of charge sharing, the charges on the capacitor at node V_x and V_y are:

Fig. 8. Circuit level implementation of proposed FTA-based IF receiver showing time-varying capacitor and SC integrator implementation, timing diagram and FIR filter coefficients.

$$Q_x = +(2m - 1)V_{IF}C_s \quad [Coulomb] \quad (3)$$

$$Q_y = -(2m - 1)V_{IF}C_s \quad [Coulomb] \quad (4)$$

where C_s is the sampling capacitance. Equation (3) and (4) show that the input V_{IF} is multiplied by a factor $\beta = (2m - 1)$. By varying 'm' from (0 to 1), the multiplying factor β can be varied from (-1 to 1). Since $\Phi_{sum} = 1$, the nodes V_x and V_y act as virtual ground and transfer the charges Q_x and Q_y to $C_{int,1}$ and $C_{int,2}$ ($C_{int,1} = C_{int,2} = C_i$), respectively. Thus, multiplication and summation are performed in this phase. Ideally, the sampling capacitor C_1 and C_2 are fully discharged (virtual ground), which is exploited to achieve 50Ω input resistance. The input resistance R_{in} of the SC circuit is approximately given by:

$$R_{in} = \frac{1}{2f_s C_s} \quad [\Omega] \quad (5)$$

The weighing and summation repeat for N cycles during $N \times T_s$; T_s is the sampling period. During this period, $\beta[n]$ varies according to FIR filter coefficients read from memory.

Sub-sampling: $\Phi_s = 1$ or 0 , $\Phi_b = 0$, $\Phi_{sum} = 0$, $\Phi_{sub} = 1$, $\Phi_{res} = 0$ and $\Phi_t = 1$. In this phase, the integrated voltage on the capacitors $C_{int,1}$ and $C_{int,2}$ are read out ($V_{OUT}[n]$). The inverter-based g_m block is sized such that it can directly drive the output (pad) capacitor C_p . In case of load variations, adding a buffer stage might be better. Thus, the IF input V_{IF} is filtered and frequency-translated to produce sub-sampled output $V_{OUT}[n]$. Since $\Phi_{sum} = 0$, no charge from the sampling capacitor is transferred to the SC integrator. The sub-sampling phase is active for $5 \times T_s$ (settling time). The output sample rate f_{sub} depends on the sampling frequency f_s and the filter length N , which would limit the BW_{BB} and cause in-band aliasing. To tackle this problem, a time-interleaved architecture is implemented, here $4 \times$, i.e. $f_{sub} = 4f_s/N$ (as discussed in Section II-B). Four TI paths are chosen such that the IBAS is at least 50 dB, as shown in Fig. 4. Compared to previous FA architectures [6], [14], [7], IBAS is improved by 47 dB.

The sampling clock Φ_s is identical for all four TI paths, while control signals are phase-shifted accordingly, using a single fixed clock system.

Reset: $\Phi_s = 1$ or 0 , $\Phi_b = 1$, $\Phi_{\text{sum}} = 0$, $\Phi_{\text{sub}} = 0$, $\Phi_{\text{res}} = 1$ and $\Phi_t = 1$. In this phase, the capacitor $C_{\text{int},1}$ and $C_{\text{int},2}$ is reset to the common mode voltage V_{cm} of the g_m block. The reset phase is active for $5 \times T_s$ (settling time).

B. Digital Architecture

A shift register-based memory is implemented to store and read the FIR coefficients and control signals. Fig. 9 shows the block diagram of the memory architecture for one of the paths (I or Q). It comprises a memory bank, a memory pointer, and a multiplexer.

The memory bank can store up to 256 words (256 FIR coefficients), each 11 bits wide (8 bits for FIR coefficients and 3 bits for control signals). It comprises four distinct memory blocks ($\text{Bank}_{[1-4]}$), each with 64 words. The input data is sequentially fed through ‘d’, while the output ($\text{Bout}_{[1-4]}$) from the four memory blocks is read out parallelly.

The primary function of the memory pointer is to update the FIR coefficients and control signals after each clock cycle. This update is accomplished by incrementing the memory bank’s address pin $\text{addr}[0:5]$. An incremental counter is used to increment the memory bank’s address every clock cycle, and it is reset after reaching the maximum count value. The maximum count value depends on filter length (N) and is set using the $\text{count}[0:5]$.

A four-phase TI FIR filter coefficients and control signals ($\text{Out}_{[1-4]}$) are generated by multiplexing the output ($\text{Bout}_{[1-4]}$) of the four memory banks. First, the filter coefficients and control signals are sliced into four parts and stored in four memory blocks ($\text{Bank}_{[1-4]}$), as shown in Fig. 10. Second, by appropriately rotating the output of the memory blocks ($\text{Bout}_{[1-4]}$) to the outputs $\text{Out}_{[1-4]}$, four phase-shifted coefficients and control signals can be realized, as shown in Fig. 10.

The outputs $\text{Out}_{[1-4]}$ each consist of 11 bits: 8 bits for FIR coefficient and 3 control signals, namely Φ_{sum} , Φ_{sub} , and Φ_{res} . These control signals may experience varying delays due to clock routing and buffer sizes, potentially causing overlap and degrading the signal. In our work, we address this by re-synchronizing $\text{Out}_{[1-4]}$ using custom D flip-flops and then buffering them with equally strong buffers. Since these control signals are programmable, we can introduce a one-clock cycle delay between them to prevent overlap conditions.

The clock-to-output delay of the digital system may potentially constrain the maximum operating clock frequency of the FTA. Fortunately, re-synchronizing and buffering techniques also help mitigate this delay requirement. However, it is worth noting that adopting custom routing and larger buffer cells can enhance the clock frequency up to 5 GHz at the expense of power [18].

IV. CIRCUIT IMPLEMENTATION, NOISE AND NON-IDEAL EFFECTS

This section will discuss the transistor-level implementation of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver. First, the time-varying

Fig. 9. Block diagram of 11-bit 256 words memory.

Fig. 10. A four-phase output control signals for four TI paths.

capacitor circuit is discussed. Second, the pseudo-differential g_m block and the SC integrator circuit design choices are discussed. Third, the noise performance of the FTA-based IF receiver is discussed. Finally, the non-idealities of the SC integrator, pre-distortion techniques used to compensate for these non-idealities and Monte Carlo (MC) simulations are discussed.

A. Circuit Implementation of Time-varying Capacitor

As discussed in the previous sections, the primary function of the time-varying capacitor is to multiply the input (V_{IF+} and V_{IF-}) with the multiplying factor β . The proposed SC multiplication is realized in two steps: first, the sampling capacitor C_1 is split into mC_1 and $(1-m)C_1$, while C_2 into mC_2 and $(1-m)C_2$, according to FIR coefficients β (ref

PMOS and NMOS strength are about equal; hence, the W/L ratio is the same, which helps to achieve higher IIP2 in this topology [21]. The transistors are biased in moderate inversion to achieve higher $(g_m/I_d) \cdot f_t$, where I_d is the bias current and f_t the transit frequency. The cross-coupled g_x and g_y pairs are designed to be $|-1/g_x| = |-1/g_y| < r_o$ so that the net output impedance is positive and the phase of the g_m block at DC is always 180° across all the corners, including mismatch.

Fig. 13 shows the simulated (post-layout) bode plot of the g_m block across all the corners. The minimum phase margin is 50° , which ensures the g_m cells are stable across the corners. The average DC gain ($A_{0,avg}$) of the g_m block is 38 dB with a standard deviation (σ_{A_0}) of 2.2 dB for a 10,000 point MC (post-layout) simulation (global and local variations). The phase of the g_m block at DC is 180° throughout the 10,000 point MC simulation, thus ensuring stability across the corners and mismatch. The simulated (post-layout) flicker noise ($1/f$) corner frequency for the g_m block is at a few tens of MHz. Since the proposed FTA-based IF receiver implements a zero/low IF architecture, an auto-zeroing technique is implemented to reduce the $1/f$ noise corner frequency.

The $A_{0,avg}$ of the g_m block can be increased by at least > 17 dB by designing g_x and g_y to be $|-1/g_x| = |-1/g_y| = r_o$. This design choice increases average DC gain but sometimes can produce a net negative impedance due to process variation. Since, the input and output nodes of the g_1 , g_2 , g_x and g_y are periodically reset to V_{cm} by switches M_{14} and M_{15} , the net negative impedance do not cause instability as long as it has higher time constant than sampling period.

The proposed FTA-based IF receiver directly samples from a 50Ω source and is designed to work at 0 V common mode input voltage. As the voltage at the node V_X and V_Y may go below 0 V, switches $M_{[8-13]}$ in Fig. 12 may turn on and leak charge from the sample capacitor C_s . To tackle this problem, the switches $M_{[8-13]}$ are implemented with high V_t transistors ($V_t \approx 420$ mV), which improves the input-compression-point by 6 dB (simulated). In contrast, the switches $M_{[14-17]}$ in Fig. 12 are implemented with ultra-low V_t transistors ($V_t \approx 247$ mV). These switches are placed after the amplifier, have a common mode voltage of approximately $VDD/2$, and do not turn on when the V_X and V_Y are below zero. Similar to sampling capacitor C_1 and C_2 , the capacitors C_b and $C_{int,[1-2]}$ are also implemented with MOM capacitors.

C. Noise

A simplified circuit model of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver for noise analysis is shown in Fig. 14. The sampling ($\Phi_s = 1$), transfer ($\Phi_s = 0$) and sub-sampling ($\Phi_{sub} = 1$) phases dominantly contribute to the total noise of the FTA-based IF receiver. The sampling and transfer phase each contribute a total integrated noise equal to $k \cdot T / C_s \cdot V^2 / Hz$, where k is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin. In addition, the differential implementation increases the total noise by a factor of 2.

Since the sampling and transfer phase noise are uncorrelated, the total integrated noise at the output V_{out} after one cycle $V_{out,1 cycle}^2$ is:

Fig. 14. Simplified circuit model of FTA-based IF receiver for noise analysis.

Fig. 15. Analytical and simulated (PSS + PNOISE) NF for different C_s and filter configuration. In this case, $N = 200$, $f_s = 1$ GHz, $C_s = C_i$, and $h_{env}[n]$ is designed for > 50 dB stop-band attenuation for both LPF and BPF configurations.

$$\overline{V_{out,1 cycle}^2} = \frac{4 \cdot k \cdot T}{C_s} \cdot \left(\frac{C_s}{C_i} \right)^2 \quad [V^2] \quad (6)$$

In the case of the FTA-based IF receiver, the sampling and transfer cycles repeat for N cycles, and hence, the total output noise increases by N , where N is the length of the FIR filter. The total integrated noise at the output V_{out} after N cycles $V_{out,N cycle}^2$:

$$\overline{V_{out,N cycle}^2} = N \cdot \frac{4 \cdot k \cdot T}{C_s} \cdot \left(\frac{C_s}{C_i} \right)^2 \quad [V^2] \quad (7)$$

The sub-sampling phase operates at rate $f_{sub} = 1 / (N \times T_s)$ (assuming one TI path). Hence, the total integrated noise $\overline{V_{out,N cycle}^2}$ in (7) is spread across $f_{sub}/2$. The noise spectral density $S_{vout}(f)$ at the node V_{out} is:

$$S_{vout}(f) = \frac{\overline{V_{out,N cycle}^2}}{f_{sub}/2} \quad [V^2/Hz] \quad (8)$$

Fig. 16. MC simulation results (global and local variations) with a 10 percent supply variation (0.81 to 0.99 V) and temperature variation (0 to 70°C) for $f_c = 200$ MHz with 100 sample points. (a) BPF TF variation, (b) HR variation, (c) Gain variation and (d) IBAS variation. (e) MC simulation results (global and local variation - only mismatch) for S_{11} variation for $f_c = 200$ MHz with 100 sample points. (f) MC simulation results (global and local variation - only mismatch) for NF variation for BPF at $f_c = 200$ MHz with 100 sample points.

An estimate of the NF (50 Ω reference) of the proposed receiver (assuming one TI path) is:

$$NF = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{S_{vout}(f)}{4 \cdot k \cdot T \cdot 50 \cdot (A_v)^2} \right) \quad [dB] \quad (9)$$

where A_v is the total voltage gain of the system. The A_v depends on the FIR filter length (N) and filter shape. In the case of BPF coefficients (as shown in Fig. 14), A_v is:

$$A_v = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_0^{N-1} h_{env}[n] \cdot \left(\frac{C_s}{C_i} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $h_{env}[n]$ is the envelope of the band-pass filter coefficients (shown in Fig. 14). The factor 1/2 accounts for the fundamental losses when the input is multiplied with a sinusoidal signal (as discussed in Section II-C). In the case of low-pass filter coefficients, A_v does not include the factor 1/2, which results in 6 dB improvement in NF for the same filtering profile $h_{env}[n]$. Fig. 15 shows the analytical and simulated NF for different C_s and filter configurations. In addition to $k \cdot T / C_s$ noise, the filtering and sinusoidal multiplication losses account for an additional NF of 8.5 dB and 6 dB, respectively. From Eq. 9, it is expected that the N does not impact the NF . However, in our design, the limited DC gain of the g_m in the SC integrator leads to additional losses in A_v , which in turn affects the NF for the higher number of coefficients.

D. Non-ideal Effect

Finite DC gain (non-ideal effect) of the g_m block in the SC integrator leads to improper charge transfer and thus affects the filter TF. This non-ideal effect can be compensated by pre-distorting the FIR filter coefficients [7]. First, a non-ideal impulse response of the proposed FTA is derived using the adjoint network technique [22], [23]. Second, pre-distorted filter coefficients are derived using the non-ideal impulse response to compensate for the non-ideal effect. The non-ideal impulse response ($h_i[n]$) of the proposed FTA (shown in Fig. 8) can be approximated by:

$$h_i[n] = - \underbrace{(2m[n] - 1) \left(\frac{C_i (A_0 + 1)}{C_s + C_i (A_0 + 1)} \right)^n}_{\beta_{non-ideal}} \left(\frac{C_s}{C_i} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$0 \leq n < N$$

where A_0 is the DC voltage gain of the g_m block and $\beta_{non-ideal}$ is the non-ideal filter coefficient ($\beta = 2m - 1$, as discussed in Section III-A). The pre-distorted filter coefficients (β_{pre}) are thus given by:

$$\beta_{pre}[n] = \frac{\beta[n]}{(\gamma)^n}, \gamma = \left(\frac{C_i (A_0 + 1)}{C_s + C_i (A_0 + 1)} \right) \quad (12)$$

The filter TF depends on the relative weight of the coefficients [7], so the $\beta_{pre}[n]$ is scaled to fit within the range (-1 to 1). Since the $A_{0,avg}$ and σ_{A_0} of the g_m block are

Fig. 17. Die photograph highlighting important blocks.

known through simulations, we can determine the range of γ to be used during measurements. As discussed in Section IV-B, the $A_{0,avg}$ of the g_m block can be improved by at least > 17 dB, which results in $\gamma \approx 1$ in (12) and eliminates the need of pre-distortion.

To mimic PVT variations, a 100-point MC simulation was done with global and local variations combined with a 10 percent supply variations and temperature variations from 0 to 70°C. Across all these MC simulations, > 50 dB stop-band attenuation (refer to Fig. 16(a)) and > 50 dB HR is achieved (refer to Fig. 16(b)). In cases with a g_m -block voltage-gain > 38 dB, no pre-distortion is needed to achieve IBAS > 50 dB. The filter-gain and IBAS shows ± 2 dB (refer to Fig. 16(c)) and ± 3 dB (refer to Fig. 16(d)), respectively. In a few cases where the g_m -block voltage-gain requirement of 38 dB was not met, the IBAS performance degrades below the 50 dB target. This relates to the spread in the cross-coupled g_m pair (g_x and g_y , shown in Fig. 12), which could be tuned by an additional supply voltage, which is not implemented here. Fortunately, the programmability of the FIR coefficients allows for pre-distortion as commonly used in RC and g_mC implementations [7] as well. To verify this, a single-trim pre-distortion calibration is performed in the aforementioned outlier MC simulations. By doing so, we were able to restore the IBAS > 50 dB in all cases. Such a pre-distortion technique would likely not be necessary in a redesign with higher voltage-gain.

V. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The proposed FTA-based IF receiver was fabricated in TSMC 28nm CMOS RF HPC+ process and bonded in a QFN 40-pin package for experimental verification. Fig. 17 shows the die photograph of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver occupying an active area of 1.36 mm². Fig. 18 shows the measurement setup. An external reference sinusoidal signal is applied to the CLK input. After amplification and frequency division by a factor of two, it is used to generate the square wave sampling clocks. An AP033 Lecroy active differential probe and Lecroy HDO6054A-MS scope are used to probe

Fig. 18. Measurement setup for the proposed SC FTA receiver.

the sampled output data, which is then processed through Matlab to obtain conversion gain and TF. The R&S FSWP50 phase noise analyzer and R&S ZVB 20 VNA are used for noise and S_{11} measurements, respectively. Both small and large signal linearity measurements are done using the spectrum analyzer and processed through Matlab. All the measurements are done at a fixed 1 GHz clock frequency (f_s), 200 MHz center frequency (f_c), 8 MHz BW and 200 filter coefficients unless specified otherwise.

A. Transfer Function and S_{11}

Fig. 19 shows the proposed FTA-based IF receiver's measured BPF transfer function, where f_c is tuned in steps of 100 MHz across the first and second Nyquist zones. Across the first Nyquist zone, the proposed FTA-based IF receiver achieves 50 dB stop-band attenuation at only $1 \times BW_{RF}$ frequency offset and 50 dB HR at all the harmonics of the f_c within the first Nyquist zone. The quantization noise of the filter coefficients limits the stop-band attenuation. Around the DC and in the second Nyquist zone near $f_s = 1$ GHz, quantization of the filter coefficients and layout parasitics between the input-output of the receiver limits the stop-band attenuation, respectively. Fig. 20 shows the BPF TF for $f_c = 200$ MHz with BW_{RF} varied from 8 MHz - 25 MHz. Fig. 21 showcases a zoomed-in version (1 MHz - 50 MHz) of the band-pass filter transfer function for $f_c = 200$ MHz presented in the Fig. 19. It compares the measured band-pass filtering profile (I and Q) with the ideal filter response (no quantization) for fixed 200 filter coefficients. The measured IBAS is 50 dB, i.e., Out of Band (OoB) blockers are suppressed by 50 dB before they fold back to signal BW_{BB} (as discussed in Section II-B and in Fig. 4). Fig. 22 shows the proposed FTA-based IF receiver's LPF transfer function for BW varied from 4 - 12.5 MHz and again achieved > 50 dB stop-band attenuation² at $1 \times BW_{RF}$ frequency offset and 50 dB IBAS. The proposed FTA-based IF receiver achieves a wideband impedance matching $S_{11} < -9$ dB across the first Nyquist zone, as shown in Fig. 23 and in Fig. 24. In the second Nyquist zone, the S_{11} degrades

²The stop-band attenuation profile of the low-pass configuration is similar to the band-pass attenuation profile, i.e., > 50 dB attenuation in the entire first Nyquist zone. Hence, a zoomed-in version (1 MHz - 50 MHz) is shown.

Fig. 19. Measured BPF TF tuned for different center frequencies across (in steps of 100 MHz) first and second Nyquist zones. In the case of $f_c = 200$ MHz, the entire stop-band attenuation profile is shown for reference.

Fig. 20. Measured BPF TF for bandwidth tuned from 8 - 25 MHz for a fixed $f_c = 200$ MHz.

Fig. 22. Measured LPF TF for bandwidth tuned from 4 - 12.5 MHz.

Fig. 21. Measured band-pass output (I and Q) and ideal TF. The second Nyquist zone aliases are suppressed by 50 dB before they fold to BW_{BB} . In this case, f_{sub} is 20 MHz, folding frequency is 10 MHz, and stop-band frequency is 15 MHz.

Fig. 23. Measured S_{11} across the first Nyquist zone.

due to the capacitive effect being dominant and achieves < -5 dB at 1 GHz (simulated). The MC simulation with both global and local variations shows ± 0.5 dB variation in the S_{11} performance at DC, as shown in Fig. 16(e).

B. Small and Large Signal Non-linearity

The proposed FTA-based IF receiver's small and large signal non-linearity is characterized using a second/third-order intercept point (IPn) and a -1 dB compression point, respectively. Fig. 25 shows the proposed receiver's small signal linearity measurements. For the in-band IIP3, two-tone $f_c + \Delta f$ and $f_c - \Delta f$ is applied at the input of the receiver, where f_c is

Fig. 24. Measured S_{11} across the Nyquist zone plotted in Smith chart (normalized to 50 Ω)

Fig. 25. Measured IB and OoB small signal linearity [IIP3 and IIP2].

the center frequency and Δf is the frequency offset. Δf is chosen such that both tones and third order Intermodulation tone (IM_3) are within the receiver's passband. The measured In-Band (IB) IIP3 is -0.6 dBm. For OoB IIP3, two tone $f_c - \Delta f$ and $f_c - 2\Delta f$ is applied to the input of the receiver. Δf , in this case, is varied from 10 - 80 MHz. The measured OoB IIP3 is 15.6 dBm at 10 MHz offset and > 18.5 dBm above 20 MHz. For OoB IIP2, $f_c + \Delta f$ and $2f_c + \Delta f$ is applied to the input of the receiver. The measured OoB IIP2 is 67 dBm at a 10 MHz offset. As IIP2 is a statistical parameter, MC simulations were performed to estimate the random IIP2 for both global and local process variations. The simulated random IIP2 is 77.45 dBm with ± 11 dBm variation at a 10 MHz offset.

Fig. 26 shows the large signal linearity measurement of the proposed receiver. For the In-band Compression Point (ICP),

TABLE I
NF FOR VARIOUS FILTER LENGTHS (N) AND FILTER CONFIGURATION

Length (N)	f_{sub} [MHz]	NF BPF [dB]		NF LPF [dB]	
		Measured	Simulated	Measured	Simulated
200	20	33.5	33	26.7	27
100	40	28.8	30	21.5	21
80	50	27.8	29	20.2	20.5

Fig. 26. Measured -1 dB compression point [ICP & B_{-1dB}].

Fig. 27. Measured output noise floor indicating 1/f corner.

a single tone at f_c is applied to the input of the receiver. The measured ICP is -12 dBm. For Blocker-induced compression point (B_{-1dB}), a single tone at $f_c + \Delta f$ is applied to the input. Δf , in this case, is varied from 10 - 80 MHz. The measured B_{-1dB} is > -11 dBm at 10 MHz offset. In the case of $f_c = 50$ MHz, 200 MHz and 400 MHz, the simulated B_{-1dB} is -2.5 dBm at an 80 MHz offset.

C. Noise and Image Rejection

As discussed in Section IV-C, the NF degrades with an increasing number of filter lengths N due to losses (limited

Fig. 28. Measured IR (gain & phase offset calibrated) across BW.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE SUMMARY AND COMPARISON WITH STATE OF THE ART SUB 1 GHz RECEIVERS

Features	RF / IF						Low IF / BB		
	This work	JSSC'17 [14]	JSSC'18 [6]	JSSC'22 [15]	JSSC'15 [4]	JSSC'13 [9]	JSSC'20 [7]	JSSC'22 [5]	
Architecture	FTA	FA	FA	FA	CT	N-path	FA-LPF	DT IIR	
Number of TI paths	4	1	2	1	NA	NA	2	NA	
Center frequency [MHz]	0 - 1000	0 - 1000	100 - 1000	100 - 1000	85 - 225	100 - 1200	NA	1.8 - 8	
Bandwidth [MHz]	8 - 25	10	2.5 - 40	5 - 20	7 - 56	8	0.06 - 3.4	2 - 15	
Stop-band attenuation [dB]	50	40 ^a	70	51	> 40 ^c	59	60	70	
Transition BW	$1 \times BW_{RF}$	$2 \times BW_{RF}$	$4 \times BW_{RF}$	$3.2 \times BW_{RF}$	$< 2 \times BW_{RF}$ ^e	$12.5 \times BW_{RF}$	$3.8 \times BW_{BB}$	$25 \times BW_{BB}$	
In-band alias suppression [dB]	50	3 ^a	3 ^a	3 ^a	NA ^d	NA	3 ^a	NA	
Number of filter coefficients (N)	80 - 200	200 ^f	200 ^f	100 ^f	NA	NA	128	NA	
OoB IIP3 [dBm] @ Δf / BW	15.6 @ 1.25	31 @ 5	21 @ 1.2	15 @ 1	24.3 @ 1	26 @ 6.25	-2.5 @ 1.6	17.3 @ > 6	
Harmonic rejection [dB]	$3f_{lo}$ & $5f_{lo}$	50	25 & 35 ^a	-	9 & 14 ^a	54 & 68	NA	NA	
	$7f_{lo}$ & $9f_{lo}$	50	40 ^a	-	-	NA	NA	NA	
NF DSB [dB]	BPF	27.8 - 33.5	26	8.5	14.1	14 - 55	2.8	22	
	LPF	20.2 - 26.7						3.5	
S_{11} [dB]	-9	0 ^a	-9	-14	NA	-5 - -8	NA	NA	
Gain [dB]	9	-12 ^a	23	10	0 - 20	25	31.5	16	
Supply voltage [V]	0.9	1.2	1.2	0.9	1.5	1.2	0.7	1	
Power [mW]	Total power	73.6 ^h	16 ^{b,h}	99 ^h	31 ^h	49.5	18 - 57.4 ^h	0.092 ^h	1.65 ^h
	Power / path	18.4	16 ^b	49.5	31 ^g	NA	NA	0.046	NA
Area [mm ²]	Total area	1.36	1.18	2.3	0.65	0.32	0.27	0.09	0.1
	Area / path	0.34	1.18	1.15	0.65	NA	NA	0.045	NA
TI paths needed to achieve IBAS > 50 dB	4	4 ^a	7 ^a	4 ^a	NA	NA	4 ^a	NA	
Power needed to achieve IBAS > 50 dB [mW]	73.6	64	346.5	124	NA	NA	0.184	NA	
Area needed to achieve IBAS > 50 dB [mm ²]	1.36	4.72	8.05	2.6	NA	NA	0.18	NA	
Technology [nm]	28	65	65	28	40	65	22	28	
Single clock architecture	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Code-independent input matching	Yes	No	No	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	

(a) estimated from figures, (b) including I and Q, (c) worst-case performance, (d) Not Applicable, (e) offset from the center frequency at which the test is performed. (f) Estimated by dividing the oversampling clock rate (f_{clk}) and sub-sampled output (f_{sub}). (g) Measured for one channel. (h) Total power consumption including clock generation and digital.

DC gain) in the SC integrator. Table. I shows the NF [dB] for BPF and LPF with various filter lengths (N). The NF of the IF receiver in the LPF configuration shows about 6 dB improvement due to the absence of factor 1/2 (sinusoidal multiplication). An extra 3 dB improvement in NF for LPF configuration is achieved by impedance scaling using two channels (I and Q). The MC simulation with both global and local variations shows +/- 1.5 dB variation in the BPF NF performance at $f_c = 200$ MHz, as shown in Fig. 16(f). Fig. 27 shows the measured output noise [dBm/Hz] for the I channel. Thanks to the auto-zeroing technique, the measured $1/f$ noise corner of the receiver is around 300 Hz.

Fig. 28 shows the measured image rejection (gain and phase offset calibrated) across the BW. The proposed FTA-based IF receiver achieves > 50 dB image rejection across the BW.

D. Performance Summary and Comparison

The performance of the proposed FTA-based IF receiver is summarized and compared with other State-of-the-Art (SoA) sub 1 GHz receivers or programmable receivers in Table. II. The receiver achieves a programmable center frequency from 0 - 1 GHz, programmable BW_{RF} from 8 - 25 MHz and $S_{11} < -9$ dB across the first Nyquist zone. The proposed receiver achieves 50 dB stop-band attenuation at only $1 \times BW_{RF}$ offset, at least $2 \times$ better than all the SoA filters. The stop-band attenuation can be further improved by increasing the number of quantization bits for the filter coefficients. The receiver

achieves 50 dB HR at all the harmonics of the f_c ($n \cdot f_c$) within the first Nyquist zone compared to prior < 25 dB HR.

The receiver also achieves a state-of-the-art IBAS of > 50 dB (shown in Fig. 21) across the signal BW. As seen from all the existing state-of-the-art FA architecture, none offers an IBAS > 3 dB, thereby necessitating additional pre-filtering to limit the alias-free bandwidth. This adds to the system's complexity and results in more silicon area and power consumption. As discussed in Section II-B, the work in [6] requires more interleaving with a total power consumption of 346.5 mW with an area > 8 mm² to also achieve IBAS > 50 dB. Similarly, sufficient interleaving for [14] would require 64 mW and 4.72 mm², and [15] would require 124 mW and 2.6 mm². Although the work in [14] might achieve IBAS > 40 dB³ with lower power, it only achieves HR < 25 dB and OoB suppression 40 dB due to parasitic capacitance in the RDAC. Our SC FTA achieves IBAS > 50 dB, HR > 50 dB and OoB suppression > 50 dB with only 74 mW and an area of 1.36 mm² (highlighted in Table. II).

From Table II, the FTA SC charge-sharing technique renders relatively good IBAS (> 50 dB), HR (> 50 dB) and OoB linearity (OoB IIP3 \approx 20 dBm), but admittedly, NF is not its strongest asset. Increased RF front-end gain can reduce cascade NF but trades it with linearity, and it depends on

³This design is restricted to 40 dB IBAS since the maximum stop-band attenuation is only 40 dB

the application whether this is good enough. If not, FTA based on a $g_m C$ or RC integrator may be preferred, as these implementations lack the charge-sharing losses (filtering and sinusoidal multiplication) that dominate NF in the proposed work (as discussed in Section IV-C). However, in the case of $g_m C$ implementation [7], the OoB IIP3 ≈ -2.5 dBm (22.5 dB less than the proposed work) is traded off for better NF performance. The RC integrator architecture [6], [14], suffers from code-dependent input matching (as discussed in Section II-F) and requires large area > 8 mm² and power ≈ 350 mW when scaled to achieve IBAS > 50 dB.

The proposed SC FTA IF receiver shows a total voltage gain of 9 dB, but it can be varied by adjusting C_i relative to C_s (see Equation. 10), e.g., by using a capacitor bank. In our work, all of these SoA functionalities, such as stop-band attenuation, HR and IBAS, are achieved with only a single fixed clock frequency, thus avoiding multi-clock domain issues.

VI. CONCLUSION

This article presents a switched-capacitor filtering and frequency translation by aliasing-based intermediate frequency receiver in 28 nm CMOS technology. This work addresses in-band alias suppression and harmonic rejection using time-interleaved architectures and sinusoidal multiplication, respectively. Thanks to the discrete-time finite impulse response architecture, the proposed receiver offers a wide range of programmability for the center frequency and bandwidth and can adapt to different intermediate frequency applications. This article also presents a mathematical analysis of the noise and non-ideal effects in switched-capacitor integrators and proposes pre-distortion techniques to compensate for the latter. Thanks to the accurate switched-capacitor charge domain weighing, the proposed intermediate frequency receiver achieves a state-of-the-art 50 dB stop-band attenuation at $1\times$ bandwidth offset, 50 dB in-band alias suppression, 50 dB harmonic rejection and 50 dB image rejection. When integrated with a baseband analog-to-digital converter, prior filtering-by-aliasing receivers only provide 3 dB in-band alias suppression. In contrast, the filtering and frequency translation by aliasing-based receiver allows for orders of magnitude improvement (> 50 dB) in in-band alias suppression, which relaxes front-end filtering requirements for intermediate frequencies.

APPENDIX A

FIR FILTER DESIGN AND BANDWIDTH CONSTRAINTS

This appendix aims to provide insight into the relation between the filter transfer function $H(f)$ and the number of filter coefficients (N). As shown in Fig. 29, for a given $H(f)$ with BW (pass-band ω_p), pass-band ripple (δ_1), stop-band attenuation (δ_2 - linear scale) and stop-band frequency (ω_s), N can be estimated as [24]:

$$N = \frac{-10 \log_{10}(\delta_1 \delta_2) - 15}{14\Delta} + 1 \quad (13)$$

where Δ is $(\omega_s - \omega_p) / 2\pi$.

To illustrate the relationship between N and BW, let's consider an example of LPF design depicted in Fig. 30 with a

Fig. 29. FIR filter transfer function terminologies.

Fig. 30. Baseband bandwidth variation due to varying number of filter coefficients

BW of 12.5 MHz (refer to BW_1 in Fig. 30), a transition band of $2\times BW_1$, and a stop-band attenuation of over 50 dB. In this scenario, the required value of N is 80. If we increase the BW to 25 MHz (refer to BW_2 in Fig. 30) (a $2\times$ increase), both ω_p and ω_s are increased by a factor of 2 to expand the BW and maintain a constant normalized transition band (i.e., $2\times BW$). This results in a $2\times$ reduction in filter coefficients, with N becoming 40, as shown in Fig. 30. Therefore, doubling the required bandwidth necessitates halving the filter coefficients to achieve the same normalized transition bandwidth.

In our circuit implementation, it's worth noting that the sub-sampling and reset phase takes 10 clock cycles (settling time), as described in Section III-A. This impacts the f_{sub} at a lower number of coefficients (< 80), thereby influencing the IBAS. Even though we could measure $BW_{RF} > 25$ MHz up to 100 MHz, we refrained from reporting this as IBAS performance would be degraded at those bandwidths for non-fundamental reasons. We reported the performance for the higher number of coefficients (80 - 200), which are the limiting factors in terms of noise and filtering shape. In an SC FTA redesign, a ping-pong architecture can be chosen to eliminate sub-sampling and reset clock cycles, resulting in higher bandwidths without compromising IBAS performance.

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